

Using *openBIS* as virtual research environment: An ELN-LIMS open-source database tool as a framework within the CRC 1411 *Design of Particulate Products*

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Abstract: The digital transformation and, thus, the use of new digital technologies not only has a substantial impact on society and companies but also on science. Analog documentation as we have known it for centuries will eventually be replaced by intelligent and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) systems. In addition to the actual research data and results, metadata now plays an important role, not only in the use of individual, independently existing projects, but also for future use by other scientists and in interdisciplinary research groups and disciplines. The solution presented here of an electronic laboratory notebook and laboratory information management system (ELN-LIMS) based on the *openBIS* (open Biology Information System) environment offers interesting features and advantages, especially for interdisciplinary work. The Collaborative Research Centre (CRC) 1411 “Design of Particulate Products” of the German Research Foundation is characterized by the cooperation of different working groups of synthesis, characterization, and simulation, and therefore serves as a model environment to present the implementation of *openBIS*. *OpenBIS*, as an open source ELN-LIMS solution following FAIR principles, provides a common set of general entries with the possibility of sharing and linking (meta-)data to improve the scientific exchange between all users.

Keywords: Open Science; Research data management; Databases; ELN-LIMS; Interdisciplinary work

1. Introduction

Digital transformation is a key challenge and has an impact on our entire society. The main players here are companies that use intelligent information technologies (IT) and networks for machines and processes (Industry 4.0). Starting with flexible production via modular, changeable production processes to customer-specific solutions and products with the help of sophisticated data acquisition, processing, and analysis (Bauernhansl et al, 2014; Lasi et al, 2014). Further examples are automation processes, machine-to-machine communication, internet-of-things (IoT) process implementation, or even augmented-reality-based workflows (Bauernhansl et al, 2014; Egger and Masood, 2020; Lasi et al, 2014; Li et al, 2015).

However, not only companies are subject to this change, but also government institutions (eGovernment) (Gisler, 2001), as well as science itself (Kimmig et al, 2021). Thus, the topic of Open

Science has become a growing movement (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (U.S.) et al, 2018), which, for example, has been supported in the European context of the *Open Research Data and Data management plans* of the *European Research Council (ERC)* established by the *European Commission* for almost five years. However, the ERC has been promoting the causes of Open Science since 2007 (ERC Scientific Council, 2021). This also manifests that open access publications from funded projects have already become mandatory to a certain extent. Exemplarily, the *DFG (German Research Foundation)* supports infrastructure projects within, e.g., *Collaborative Research Centres (CRCs)*, as long-term university-based research institutions, established for up to 12 years, whose funding objective is to establish powerful information systems for research in a holistic perspective (German Research Foundation, 2021). Nevertheless, the topic of Open Science includes more than just the public provision of data in the sense of open access publications, but also in the approaches of open methodology, sources, and data. The necessary implementation and representation of good scientific data management, data quality, and stewardship (data governance) are tremendously important (Brous et al, 2016; Hildebrand et al, 2011; Ladley, 2020; Wilkinson et al, 2016). The resulting benefits can be measured directly, e.g., in terms of improvements in process efficiency or cost and risk reductions, and indirectly, such as increased acceptance, perception, and trust (Brous et al, 2016; Hildebrand et al, 2011; Tallon, 2013).

One of the cornerstones of this overall research data management (RDM) is the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). The emphasis placed on growing awareness of FAIRness is, however, more than just an essential duty that public funding agencies impose on research, but, moreover, it is the key to conduct knowledge discovery, innovation, and transfer, as well as the subsequent integration and reuse by the scientific community (Wilkinson et al, 2016). Events such as the global Corona pandemic demonstrate the need for, and the overall benefits of, making data and enable online availability (Besançon et al, 2021; Tse et al, 2020). This leads not only to efficient research and increased innovation, but also to fair and transparent use of public funds and tax money, as well as increased visibility and scientific reputation and reliability, to name just a few benefits of Open Science (Janssen et al, 2012).

Figure 1. Key parameters based on data stewardship principles like data accessibility, availability, integrity, (re-)usability, and security (FAIR principles). This figure is adapted from (Plass, Fabian, 2022).

One of the tools used by researchers to publish not only publications but also scientific data and general information are data repositories. Well-known examples are the commercial data

repository service *figshare* (<http://figshare.com>), open access archives like *arXiv.org* or platforms like *DataVerse* (Crosas, 2011), *EUData* (Lecarpentier et al, 2013), *Zenodo* (<http://zenodo.org/>), which is maintained by *CERN* and funded by the *EU Commission*. In fact, most of the known repositories already consider the high-level FAIR principle. So, in the case of *Zenodo*, the uploaded data is provided with a digital object identifier (DOI) can optionally be published as open-accessible and viewable (CC BY 4.0 Creative Commons (<https://creativecommons.org/>) license). This, in turn, leads to simplified findability, accessibility, and usability for the scientific community, as well as to the quotability of individual datasets, whose content no longer has to lead directly to a complete publication. This means that even data, methods, or code that initially received little attention can now be found by the general public and are not lost. Moreover, the principles of good research practice still apply.

However, justified doubts exist regarding the Open Science policy. Especially, there are questions and concerns about the security of data against external interference and possible compliance and regulatory requirements, especially in healthcare, such as the protection of relevant patient data. These issues circling around the subject of data sovereignty need to be clarified during the planning and before introducing digital technologies such as data management or cloud-based systems (Clayton et al, 2019; Hummel et al, 2021).

Good research data management does not start with the publication and archiving process of the work or the (meta-)data, but with their initial collection. This is because not only content-related data/information is of importance in the sense of RDM, but also its metadata. Metadata describes data or in general (additional) information about the described data(set). Metadata-specific information can be, e.g., the author, the creation time/date or the type of the dataset, as well as the DOI of the dataset. In fact, many distinct types of metadata exist, including descriptive, structural, as well as administrative or process data related information.

However, the scientific question, the choice of an experimental procedure, the materials and methods, the data analysis, and the interpretation of the results are traditionally recorded in detail in notebooks on paper and not electronically (Barillari et al, 2016). Not only is this incomprehensible, since most data are generated electronically or stored as code on a network anyway, but this concept vehemently contradicts the overarching principles of FAIR and Open Science in general. Neither are the data easy to find, nor are they accessible or usable by scientists outside the local system in which they are stored. Inevitably, the use of paper-based notebooks should be avoided, and a shift made to electronic systems such as a laboratory information management system (LIMS) and/or an electronic laboratory notebook (ELN). ELN systems, for example, can play a major role in a successful RDM. In this way, a continuous workflow under FAIR conditions can be guaranteed from the very beginning, starting with the collection of data, the use of the data by oneself or the research group and other researchers, the publication of the data, and finally a superior archiving, for example of data repositories like *Zenodo* or *RADAR* (Kraft et al, 2016). Further advantages of an ELN system are obvious: starting with (i) the easy and metadata-based collection of information, as well as their shareability, (ii) an ensured long-lasting data storage on a secured server, (iii) simplified accessibility via a global or local network, as well as (iv) the archiving possibilities on open data repositories and (v) self-implementable applications with the system (Barillari et al, 2016). Currently available ELN systems range from commercial applications like *CERF* (<https://cerf-notebook.com/>), *Benchling* (<https://www.benchling.com/>) or *labfolder* (<https://www.labfolder.com/>) or open-source-based ones like *chemotion* (<https://www.chemotion.net/chemotionsaurus/>), *eLabFTW* (<https://www.elabftw.net/>) or *openBIS* (<https://openbis.ch/>).

The scope of Open Science and research data management, as well as a clear and well-defined data stewardship and governance, has been clearly recognized from the perspective of the

DFG-funded *CRC 1411 Design of Particulate Products*. However, an ELN-LIMS is currently lacking for the use within an interdisciplinary field between engineering, material sciences, natural sciences, mathematics, theoretical modeling and simulation. Furthermore, commercial systems are generally not recommended by the possible financial conditions, in addition to a thereby complementary Open Science policy. Open-source products like *chemotion* are, again, too subject-specific (here in the particular case chemistry), which would lead to a less beneficial impact on interdisciplinary work and research, such as lower usability, and, thus, in the end, also acceptance in other subject groups. The *openBIS* system of the *Department of Biosystems Science and Engineering and Biology* of the *ETH Zurich* (Barillari et al, 2016; Bauch et al, 2011), on the other hand, shows some promising features that are worth a closer look, even though this system was designed primarily for biological and medical disciplines and is used not only by academic institutions but also by companies in the industry sector (Bauch et al, 2011).

Accordingly, we describe our system in several subsections, starting with the basic principles and working features of *openBIS*, continuing with the goals and requirements of researchers within the CRC and the scientific community for a well-functioning ELN tool, and ending with its implementation and usage. In addition, we also want to share our experiences in further developing the system and its implementation and daily use.

2. Results

2.1. General overview and structure of *openBIS*

Before we shed light on how *openBIS* can help us with a successful implementation of a beneficial RDM, we first clarify i) what *openBIS* is, ii) how it works, and iii) what technical requirements need to be met. *OpenBIS* is an open-source platform that functions both as an Electronic Laboratory Notebook (ELN) and as a Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS). Developed by *ETH Zurich*, *openBIS* provides an open-source database for research laboratories, especially designed and implemented in and for life sciences (Barillari et al, 2016). The goal was to build a simple and efficient, yet comprehensive ELN-LIMS system that meets the daily needs of a research institution. Everyday things like storage of materials, instrumental setups and devices, the acquisition, description, and processing of large amounts of data, and the forwarding to possible users and scientists within the *openBIS* system should be possible (Bauch et al, 2011).

However, what kind of technical conditions are needed to build *openBIS* within a research group? And is *openBIS* scalable at all? Is a comprehensive *openBIS* system in the area of a scientific network (EU or DFG fund) or possibly a comprehensive database within an entire university even conceivable? All of these questions are important to know before starting with an ELN-LIMS and will be discussed in the following subsections accordingly.

The history of *openBIS* and its platform, on which it is based, started in 2007 and is still actively maintained, nowadays by the *Scientific IT Service Team* of the *ETH Zurich*. As operating system (OS), *openBIS* requires a modern Unix-like OS, for instance Linux systems, but is mainly platform-independent, though. A very interesting and detailed look on the general technical background of *openBIS* is provided by the developers, accordingly (Bauch et al, 2011). Therefore, shortly summarized, in *openBIS*, an *Application Server (AS)* and one or several *Data Store Server(s) (DSS)* are introduced. On the *AS*, data provenance actions like metadata handling are conducted while on the *DSS*, the raw data is managed. While, exemplarily, the user access is facilitated via a web browser, the *AS* uses a *Relational Database Management System (RDBMS)* to generate persistent information like index information about all data sets, the data itself is covered and stored within the (several) *DSS* system(s). The latter is responsible for creating, querying, and visualizing data while they are mediated by the *AS* (Bauch et al, 2011).

2.2. Features of openBIS as ELN-LIMS system

As *openBIS* is accessible for users via a web app, accessible even from outside the university network, access to the user's own data and data provided by others is guaranteed always and everywhere. It is not only crucial to be able to create and implement (meta-)data, but further enables the function that every user can permit access to his projects to selected users. This covers different *roles* (observer, user, admin) with different rights like reading, writing or even deleting. The authorization process lies here completely in the hands of each user and can be adjusted independently – with respect to other users within the network or other projects by the same user. In general, *openBIS* has a predefined hierarchical structure, which is divided into several levels: The first and overall level is the *Work or Data Space* level, which, in addition to general rights and access, primarily contains all *Projects*, and the second level, which means the projects themselves. These, in turn, have for example *Collections* (third level), which in turn consist of different *Object Types* (fourth level), with/without *Datasets* (see also Figure 2), like *Experimental Step*, *Entry* or *Instrument* (Bauch et al, 2011). This is also valid for *Collections*. In fact, the first and second level are hardcoded, which means that due to the persistent identifier only *one* specific path with the nomenclature “/user(workspace)/projectx” exists. Moreover, following our example, we can move *Collection 1* with all his containing entries to *Project 2*, but not vice versa. Moreover, object types (like *OBJ 3*) can be

used by collections several times, as stated in Figure 2. This in fact reduces redundancy.

Figure 2. Logical structure layers of *openBIS* containing the *Work- or Data space*, *Projects*, *Collections*, *Object Types (OBJs)*, and attached *Datasets* (red). This figure is adapted from Barillari, C., et al. (Barillari et al, 2016).

Limitations like a maximum of users working one *openBIS* ELN system are not existing. The only limitations are connected to the available and used server resources. But, how can we connect data regarding samples, materials, instruments, and experiments with each other, as a good ELN-LIMS system should be built on the FAIR principles? Here, *openBIS* features the *parent-child relationship* model (see also Figure 3 for further detail): This means that every created *Object type* is somehow logically interconnected between other *Object types*. As an example of our CRC, synthesis and characterization groups are trying to develop specific and well-defined particles considering different synthetic samples, materials, and processes. To ensure that the creation, modification, or deletion of any electronic records is traceable, computer-generated, and time-stamped audit trails

are used to record the date and time of the user's intervention. As an example, to create an *Experimental Step X* and *Y* (see also Figure 3), the researcher/user requires a different amount of *Samples A* and *B*, as well as one specific *Instrument I*. Moreover, for a specific *Simulation Z*, one uses *Sample B* and *Software S*. Here, *Sample*, *Instrument*, *Software*, as well as the *Experimental Step* and *Software* or later on *Publication* are all different created *Object types* that are accessible and existing for every user of our *openBIS* system. Furthermore, all *Object Types* within our system are classified into three different categories and differ if they are generalized entries (*Entry* and *General Type*), experimental procedures or analysis (like *Experimental Step* or *Simulation*) or properties and (real existing) objects (like *Instrument* or *Software*). In our basic examples, it is valid that *Sample A* and *B*, *Instrument I*, and *Software S* are all *parents* of the *Experimental step X*, *Y*, and *Simulation Z*, respectively, which are automatically the *child(ren)* of the prior *Object types*. If we now create an *Object type Publication P*, which is linked and fed via our *Experimental step X*, *Y*, and *Simulation Z*, then accordingly, *P* is the *child* of *X*, *Y*, and *Z*, and vice versa. This results in a clear and well-understandable line of ancestry, which fulfills the FAIR concept. In our example, even after publishing (*Publication P*), one can clearly find and reuse (meta-)data of the corresponding project. Moreover, one has not to create object types (and their underlying (meta-)data) multiple times, as one can reuse them, if needed, infinitely. This can save not only a lot of time, but also leads to the possibility to create and implement a more comprehensible laboratory and research system.

The parents-children relation

Figure 3. The hierarchical structure of the parents-children relation in action. Every object type (for example *Sample*, *Experimental Step*, and *Publication*) is child and parent depending on its ancestry relation. In our example, *Publication P* is child of every other object type like *Instrument I* or *Experimental Step X*.

OpenBIS can also be used not only in labs, but also for administrative and lab-specific workflow processes. To understand how, we have to take one step back and need to consider how *openBIS* works from each user's point of view of. First of all, every user possesses his own *Workspace*, which can be compared to his own desktop or computer storage. Within this *Workspace*, he can create and adjust projects, metadata, etc., without necessarily being connected to other users. However, as mentioned above, this is possible using the *Grant access* option. All now permitted users will appear as folder icons below the own *Workspace* folder icon. However, one researcher or user is connected to a specific working group or institute containing several other researchers/users. So, how can we bring the entire working group together without multiple times pressing the *grant access* button, as well as to define the user roles? Especially for general

administrative or instruments within the institute, which are accessible for every researcher of the corresponding group, creating for example several *Instrument* object types is not only time-consuming, but also hold the danger of creating different metadata for the same, here exemplarily, instrument. This would result in problems with the FAIR principle.

Consequently, *openBIS* has an additional workspace area called *Inventory*, which in turn can be divided into several different fields like administrative work processes, instruments, materials, etc. Moreover, as now every user has access to the, exemplarily *Instrumentation* folder section within the *Inventory*, one only has to create each *Instrument* object type (for example, *I1*, *I2*, ...) one time, while it can be used by each user within the working group (the access-permitted users for this specific *Instrument* section folder). In fact, like this, it is possible to combine a classical working group environment with interdisciplinarity and FAIR data management within an overall framework.

2.3. *openBIS* as a multi-institutional framework within a material science-based environment – Adjustments and Experiences

This multi-institutional framework can now be implemented and customized to your own needs. Via an additional overlay (*Core UI*), the implementation of different object types (from simple general types to specifically customized types) is possible. But how many or which types should be implemented? Are more and, thus, very specific and fine-tuned types preferable or not? These questions will arise during implementation and should be clarified in advance. Since there is no golden rule, each scientific environment and community should be treated differently.

In our case, we decided to form a pilot group for all users within the *CRC 1411* about six months before handing the *openBIS* system over to the entire group. Since our interdisciplinary working environment consists of different disciplines, from pure particle synthesis to their characterization, analysis, simulation, and theoretical optimization, we invited about fifteen people from the different working groups/disciplines and implemented, discussed, and modified our preliminary system up to this point, so that everyone was satisfied with the result. It turned out that implementing dozens of different and fine-tuned object types for each user, while appearing functional at first sight, also brings some disadvantages, because while each (overall) object type is visible in the drop-down menu, not every object type is used by every user. For example, theoretical scientists, who use mathematical models to simulate and predict physical properties of potential nanoparticles, rarely use synthesis-based object types like *General Protocol* or *Experimental Step*. This means that any user from a particular discipline will only stick to the types that are useful for their own research. Furthermore, since each type is always present in the system's drop-down menu, it quickly becomes cluttered and confusing, leading to poorer usability and, consequently, a less accepted package. So, this should be avoided. Therefore, we finally decided to use only eleven object types, two of which (*Entry* and *Experimental Step*) are already preset by the developers, while eight types contain specific (meta-)data and one which is defined as an overall or general object type (*General Type*).

But how can we meet requirements, such as scientific or administrative needs, which may even exist within the same discipline? Again, our implemented multi-institutional framework could help. Now, that each workgroup/environment has its own "space" within the overall *openBIS* system, it is possible to implement specific "workgroup-defined object types". For example, in our *CRC 1411*, synthesis and processes can vary between workgroups, so implementing finely tuned objects, which can only be used by users within that workgroup or users with access privileges, is preferable. Furthermore, there are no negative effects, such as usability on interdisciplinary work or traceability of (meta-)data, since, within the entire *openBIS* system (and users with access rights), the new (and now workgroup-specific) types can still be viewed. As a result, this leads to a balanced combination

of a universal and well-usable *openBIS* data management system and a well-tailored work environment. In addition, the FAIR principles and good research policy still apply.

Reality vs. proposal

Figure 4. Current joint venture project within the CRC 1411 between synthesis (project group A05) and theoretical simulation (project group D05). The “real” scheme (hierarchy graph) as a clear and distinct option for relation-based process structures. The picture on the left is filtered and shortened for better clarification and visibility. The right scheme depicts the proposed structure of our CRC relating to the joint venture project of A05 (red) and D05 (violet circles).

Now each user can edit and share their own data, both scientific and non-scientific in nature/origin, with themselves or with other users within the *openBIS* system by creating and storing data and metadata. But now the question arises how these data can be exported in turn? The reasons for this can be quite different: More and more journals are demanding that special attention needs to be paid to Open Science and research data management, e.g., by using a data repository to which publication-specific (meta)-data must be uploaded and made freely available to all. In some journals, for example, it is common to prepare a data availability statement when submitting the publication. This statement includes information about the data itself, where to find it, an identifier for the data (DOI or Persistent Identifier), and how to access the data. However, how can the stored data on the *openBIS* server be downloaded and re-exported? Furthermore, what data formats are existing/present in which the (meta)-data can be exported? The function used for this is the *Export Metadata & Data* function. The *openBIS* server now plays the role of a kind of e-mail distributor. That is, *openBIS* exports the project folder selected by the user as a *.zip* file, which now contains all (meta)-data, as *.txt*, *.doc*, *.html*, and *.json* files, as well as the introduced structure. Since each user has his own account in *openBIS*, the user can send the exported file to others directly to their e-mail inbox by entering their e-mail address. This *.zip* file can now be attached to a publication as Supplementary or Supporting Information or uploaded to a data repository, and the DOI thus obtained can be noted in the actual publication. This closes the entire research data management data lifecycle, from project inception through data production and analysis to long-term archiving. Moreover, the pre-structured organization of your project(s) on *openBIS* (and via the *Object types*) stays the same after export. That means that no additional structuring process is needed. Furthermore, after implementation of the gathered publication or research papers that have been published under the *CRC 1411* roof, we track all of them via *openBIS* now as well.

Our current *openBIS* system has been up and running for a few months now (since end of December 2021), but we are still testing new features and making minor and major changes. Following the roll-out of the “final” version of the *openBIS* system to our users within the *CRC 1411*, we have organized several introductory events within our *IRTG* (integrated Research Training Group).

In addition, we host monthly support meetings where questions or comments can be brought forward, and support is offered. Furthermore, we did not want to develop an exclusive data management system, so young research students, e.g., in the context of their Bachelor's or Master's thesis, will have access as new users to get in touch with research data management. In addition, the existing benefits for students and their supervisors or research colleagues remain, so sluggish use of our *openBIS* system has not really been the case, even in the early days, immediately after the roll-out. Rather, the purchase of lab notebooks/tablets has increased the adoption of *openBIS*, as data creation, processing and sharing within the labs is now very fast and easy. The use of paper-based laboratory notebooks has been decreasing significantly over time.

3. Conclusions

We demonstrate an ELN-LIMS solution that addresses the challenges and needs of multiple disciplines within a technical and natural science faculty on the *openBIS* system. In fact, the versatility and modifiability of the system formed the basis for a system for multiple working groups of the *CRC 1411 Design of Particulate Products* that meets the documentation needs of groups focusing on synthesis, characterization, and simulation, and, in particular, supports collaboration between different disciplines within the CRC. The structure was developed and adapted via several steps and provides both a common set of *Object types* and the ability to include more specific ones for individual working groups without disrupting common workflows. Ultimately, this ELN-LIMS could serve as a template solution for other similarly structured collaborative research centers or research groups.

Supplementary Materials: The aim of this research article is not only to show what *openBIS* can do in the interdisciplinary research environment, but also how metadata and data are ultimately presented. Therefore, as an example project, the development of the research article "*Using openBIS as virtual research environment: An ELN-LIMS open-source database tool as a framework within the CRC 1411 "Design of Particulate Products"*" was connected via *openBIS* to the necessary/received metadata and data and a clear structure was developed. The data received through *openBIS* as exported *.zip* files contain four different data types of each existing/used object type and folder, organized in a clear folder-subfolder structure. Typical standard data types used here include *.doc*, *.txt*, *.json*, and *.html*. Attached data (as *Datasets*) to its corresponding object type is additionally linked as subfolder.

References

- Barillari, C, Ottoz, D S, Fuentes-Serna, J M, Ramakrishnan, C, Rinn, B, and Rudolf, F** 2016 openBIS ELN-LIMS: an open-source database for academic laboratories. *Bioinformatics*, 32(4): 638–640. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btv606>
- Bauch, A, Adamczyk, I, Buczek, P, Elmer, F-J, Enimanev, K, Glyzewski, P, Kohler, M, Pylak, T, Quandt, A, Ramakrishnan, C, and others** 2011 openBIS: a flexible framework for managing and analyzing complex data in biology research. *BMC bioinformatics*, 12(1): 1–19. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-12-468>
- Bauernhansl, T, Ten Hompel, M, and Vogel-Heuser, B** 2014 *Industrie 4.0 in Produktion, Automatisierung und Logistik - Anwendung · Technologien · Migration*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden.

Besaçon, L, Peiffer-Smadja, N, Segalas, C, Jiang, H, Masuzzo, P, Smout, C, Billy, E, Deforet, M, and Leyrat, C 2021 Open science saves lives: lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 21(1): 117. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-021-01304-y>

Brous, P, Janssen, M, and Vilminko-Heikkinen, R 2016 Coordinating Decision-Making in Data Management Activities: A Systematic Review of Data Governance Principles. In: Scholl, H J, Glassey, O, Janssen, M, Klievink, B, Lindgren, I, Parycek, P, Tambouris, E, Wimmer, M A, Janowski, T, and Sá Soares, D (eds.), *Electronic Government*. Cham: Springer International Publishing. pp. 115–125. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-44421-5_9

Clayton, E W, Evans, B J, Hazel, J W, and Rothstein, M A 2019 The law of genetic privacy: applications, implications, and limitations. *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, 6(1): 1–36. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lisz007>

Crosas, M 2011 The dataverse network®: an open-source application for sharing, discovering and preserving data. *D-lib Magazine*, 17(1/2). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1045/january2011-crosas>

Egger, J and Masood, T 2020 Augmented reality in support of intelligent manufacturing – A systematic literature review. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 140: 106195. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2019.106195>

ERC Scientific Council 2021 Open Research Data and Data Management Plans. Available at https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_info_document-Open_Research_Data_and_Data_Management_Plans.pdf [Last accessed 15 February 2022].

German Research Foundation 2021 Guidelines Collaborative Research Centres. Available at https://www.dfg.de/formulare/50_06/50_06_en.pdf [Last accessed 17 October 2022].

Gisler, M (ed.) 2001 *E-Government. 1: Eine Standortbestimmung / [1. Schweizer e-Government-Symposium am 22. August 2000 in Zürich]. Michael Gisler ... (Hrsg.). 2., aktualisierte Aufl.* Presented at the Schweizer eGovernment-Symposium, Bern Stuttgart Wien: Haupt.

Hildebrand, K, Gebauer, M, Hinrichs, H, and Mielke, M (eds.) 2011 *Daten- und Informationsqualität*. Wiesbaden: Vieweg+Teubner. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-8348-9953-8>

Hummel, P, Braun, M, Tretter, M, and Dabrock, P 2021 Data sovereignty: A review. *Big Data & Society*, 8(1): 205395172098201. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951720982012>

Janssen, M, Charalabidis, Y, and Zuiderwijk, A 2012 Benefits, Adoption Barriers and Myths of Open Data and Open Government. *Information Systems Management*, 29(4): 258–268. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10580530.2012.716740>

Kimmig, J, Zechel, S, and Schubert, U S 2021 Digital Transformation in Materials Science: A Paradigm Change in Material's Development. *Advanced Materials*, 33(8): 2004940. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202004940>

Kraft, A, Razum, M, Potthoff, J, Porzel, A, Engel, T, Lange, F, Van den Broek, K, and Furtado, F 2016 The RADAR Project—A Service for Research Data Archival and Publication. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 5(3). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi5030028>

Ladley, J 2020 *Data governance: how to design, deploy and sustain an effective data governance program*. Second edition. London [England] ; San Diego, CA: Academic Press.

Lasi, H, Fettke, P, Kemper, H-G, Feld, T, and Hoffmann, M 2014 Industry 4.0. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 6(4): 239–242. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12599-014-0334-4>

Lecarpentier, D, Wittenburg, P, Elbers, W, Michelini, A, Kanso, R, Coveney, P, and Baxter, R 2013 EUDAT: a new cross-disciplinary data infrastructure for science. *International Journal of Digital Curation*, 8(1): 279–287. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v8i1.260>

Li, S, Xu, L D, and Zhao, S 2015 The internet of things: a survey. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 17(2): 243–259. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-014-9492-7>

National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (U.S.), National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (U.S.), National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (U.S.), and National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (U.S.) (eds.) 2018 *Open science by design: realizing a vision for 21st century research*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press.

Plass, Fabian 2022 Research Data Management in the CRC 814 – A short introduction. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6389908>

Tallon, P P 2013 Corporate Governance of Big Data: Perspectives on Value, Risk, and Cost. *Computer*, 46(6): 32–38. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2013.155>

Tse, E G, Klug, D M, and Todd, M H 2020 Open science approaches to COVID-19. *F1000Research*, 9: 1043. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.26084.1>

Wilkinson, M D, Dumontier, M, Aalbersberg, IJ J, Appleton, G, Axton, M, Baak, A, Blomberg, N, Boiten, J-W, da Silva Santos, L B, Bourne, P E, and others 2016 The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3(1): 1–9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>